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Identifying gender stereotyping using text analysis

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Introduction

Language use can be interpreted as an expression of opinions and attitudes of the speaker or author, and therefore studying language use can inform us about social phenomena (Pennebaker 2011), and the many texts produced within the science system science are no exception (e.g. Madera et al 2009; Markowitz 2019; Van den Besselaar et al 2018): peer review reports of scientific articles, evaluation reports used within selection processes for academic positions, and reports used in the evaluation of research programs, groups and organizations, and in grant selection. When accessible, these texts can provide us with a rich source to study what evaluation criteria are used, which are more and less important, how the evaluation proceeds, and whether the evaluators suffer from biases (Van den Besselaar et al 2018; Van den Besselaar & Mom 2021b). Also the analysis of the language used in scientific papers or of grant or job applications may reveal interesting phenomena, especially related to the self-presentation of the authors.

In this paper we focus on the analysis of texts in grant applications procedures. We discuss briefly earlier work on how text analysis informs about the ‘logic’ of the grant evaluation process, and then address the two main question of this paper:

- Can *peer review texts* be used to study gender bias in the grant selection process?
- Do gender differences in the language *of grant applications* – so in self-presentation - explain gender bias in the panel scores for those applications?

Evaluation of grant proposals

In earlier work (Van den Besselaar et al 2018, 2016) we showed that text analysis of the review reports does inform about the nature of the grant evaluation processes and about the criteria deployed. Using a large set of review reports covering almost all disciplines we found that the percentage of words in an evaluation report that refer to the *proposal* and the *achievements* of the applicant correlates negatively with the scores the proposal receive. This can be explained by the well-known fact that if there is disagreement in a small group (the selection panel), the discussions are longer, and therefore more words are used (Festinger 1950). Furthermore, negative terms correlate negatively, and positive terms correlate positively with the scores,

which would be expected. But interestingly, the effect of the *negative terms* on the scores is much stronger than the effect of *positive terms*, suggesting that the focus of the review process in our case is much more on the weaknesses of applications or PIs and much less on identifying their strengths. Table 1 shows some of the results. Similar studies are needed to find out whether that is a general feature of grant review processes, or that this depends on different contextual factors. This we aim to study in a current project on gender disparities in grant decisions and academic careers: The GRANteD project (www.granted-project.eu).

Table 1:

Project-score (first phase) by frequency of linguistic categories

Model 5	Unstandardized		Standardized		Sig.	95.0% Conf interv for <i>B</i>	
	<i>B</i>	SE	Beta	<i>t</i>		Lower Bnd	Upper Bnd
(Constant)	3.337	0.058		57.91	0	3.224	3.450
Negation	− 0.487	0.025	− 0.544	− 19.446	0	− 0.536	− 0.438
Negative evaluation	− 0.159	0.019	− 0.197	− 8.24	0	− 0.196	− 0.121
Exclusion	0.093	0.02	0.121	4.756	0	0.055	0.131
Superlatives	0.095	0.014	0.115	6.942	0	0.068	0.121
Proposal	− 0.041	0.005	− 0.102	− 7.429	0	− 0.051	− 0.03
Track record	− 0.056	0.009	− 0.085	− 6.065	0	− 0.074	− 0.038
Certainty	0.193	0.04	0.065	4.884	0	0.116	0.271
Disagreement	− 0.147	0.032	− 0.059	− 4.588	0	− 0.209	− 0.084
Positive evaluation	0.033	0.01	0.056	3.334	0.001	0.014	0.052
Positive emotions	0.035	0.01	0.050	3.396	0.001	0.015	0.056
Negative emotions	− 0.031	0.014	− 0.029	− 2.203	0.028	− 0.058	− 0.003
Adjusted $R^2 = 0.507$							

N= 2926

Table 2:

Linguistic categories by performance scores

	NJCS journal impact	Top 5% cited papers	# Grants	Quality network	# Intern. co-authors	# Co-authors
Positive evaluation		0.151**		0.136*		
Superlatives			0.134**	0.162**		- 0.114*
Certainty	0.113*	0.111*				0.116*
Positive emotion					0.108*	- 0.214**
Negative evaluation	- 0.304**	- 0.199**	- 0.186**	- 0.267**	- 0.108*	
Negation	- 0.334**	- 0.234**	- 0.197**	- 0.302**	- 0.121*	
Exclusion	- 0.257**	- 0.170**	- 0.134*	- 0.239**		
Track record	- 0.197**	- 0.135**		- 0.175**		- 0.341**
Proposal	- 0.171**	- 0.103*		- 0.127*		0.119*
Agentic				0.131*		- 0.193**
Achievement						- 0.187**

Four life science panels, phase 1: $N = 348$;

*Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

We also found that word use in the review reports correlates with the past performance of the applicants (Table 2). The positive terms correlate positively and the negative terms negatively with most of the bibliometric scores, suggesting that past performance influences the opinion of the reviewers. And the frequency of project related terms and achievement related terms also correlate negatively with the bibliometric indicators. This suggests that if an applicant has lower bibliometric scores, there is more attention during the evaluation for the track record and for the project proposal. And as we showed in Table 1, this results in a lower score for both the project proposal and the PI's achievements.

Language, gender stereotyping, and gender bias

The previous analysis did not look at gender differences, but the language of review reports may show whether peer reviewers and panel members in grant allocation procedures are (gender) biased. Gender bias is often based on gender stereotyping, which is reflected in the use of language (Ellemers 2018; Beukeboom 2014). When reviewers use gender stereotypes, one can expect gender bias in the selection process (Ellemers 2018; Varian 1999; Steward & Valian 2018; Van den Besselaar & Mom 2021, 2021b). Gender stereotyping may be identified in language in different ways:

- *Negation* terms in review reports not only indicate negative evaluations of applicants but also reflect gender stereotypes about women. This is related to the distinction between ingroups and outgroups. As the stereotypical scientist is male, men are the ingroup and female are the outgroup. And the outgroup is more often described in negative terms, whereas the ingroup is described in positive terms: *He is good* versus *she is not bad*. As gender stereotyping may lead to gender bias against women, one would expect that the higher the share of negation words in panel review reports about women, the stronger the gender bias against women in the panel scores of that panel. This would imply that the frequency of negation words correlates negatively with the

scores the grant proposals receive, and this effect is stronger for women than for men. In the following analysis we use next to negation terms also *superlatives*.

- The frequency of *agentic* terms (Madera et al, 2009) can be used to identify gender stereotyping. Agentic characteristics are considered important for scientists, but at the same time, in terms of gender stereotypes men are expected to show agentic characteristics whereas this is much less expected for women. Above that, if women show agentic characteristics this may even be assessed negatively, as those are seen as desirable characteristics for men but as undesirable for women (Ellemers 2018). Therefore, one would expect that women are differently assessed in terms of agentic terms than men. More precisely, the more panels use agentic terms for women, the higher the gender bias against women in the panel decisions, and the more panels use agentic terms for men, the higher the gender bias in favor of men, and against women. For *communal terms*, it would work in the opposite way.

Data and method

For the current paper, we use a sample of some 2500 grant applications in 22 review panels. The performance data and the linguistic data were standardized at the panel level, in order to control for disciplinary differences in publishing and writing styles.

We measured the level of gender bias in the panels in the following way (Van den Besselaar & Mom 2021b): A regression analysis was used to predict the scores and grant success using a variety of merit variables (bibliometric indicators, (international) coauthors, number of earlier grants, ranking of the organization the researcher is affiliated with) and personal variables (such as biological age and academic age). The expected probabilities were compared to the realized probabilities for women to receive a grant at the panel level, and the difference between the two probabilities is the bias indicator. The question then is whether the language of the panel review texts is correlated with the score the proposal did receive.

Then we did a regression analysis with mediation, in order to find out whether language use (and therefore stereotyping) explains a part of the gender differences in the panel scores. Finally, we also analyzed whether gender differences in the textual presentation of the research proposal explains the gender differences in the panel scores, using a model developed earlier (Van den Besselaar & Mom 2022), but here reformulated as a mediation model.

Preliminary findings

(i) *Gender stereotyping by panel members*

Analyzing the review reports at the panel level (Van den Besselaar & Mom 2021b) showed a positive correlation between the level of gender bias against women and the frequency of negation terms used in the evaluation reports of female applicants ($r = 0.480$, $p = 0.024$). And the larger the difference between the frequency of negation terms in evaluations of women compared to men, the larger is the level of gender bias against women ($r=0.564$), again at panel level.

We also found a positive relation between the gender bias against women the use of agentic terms in reviews about men ($r = 0.312$), implying that the more agentic terms in the review, the higher bias *in favor* of men, and *against women*. For women we find an even stronger correlation between gender bias against women and the use of agentic terms ($r = 0.543$, $p =$

0.032). So, the more agentic terms, the higher bias *against* women (and in favor of men). This suggests that when agentic characteristics are discussed, it is done in a positive way for men, but in a negative way for women.

(ii) *Is gender bias in panel scores mediated by stereotypes?*

If gender stereotyping is a main factor producing gender bias, then one would expect that language use would be a mediating factor between gender and the scores applicants get. The following model represents this:

Figure 1: Panel score by gender and language use in review text as mediator

In order to test the model, we conducted a mediation analysis (linear regression), resulting in the following regression coefficients (table 3): (1) Men have a significantly higher score (beta = 0.08, $p=0$). (2) Reviews about male applicants have significantly more superlatives (beta = 0.055, $p=.003$) and reviews of women have significantly more negation terms (beta = $-.042$, $p=.021$), more communal terms (Beta = $-.034$, $p=.065$) and more agentic terms, although this is not significant. (3) The multiple regression shows that all language categories have a significant effect on the panel score, as does gender. However, the effect of gender is much lower than in analysis (1): 0.033 versus 0.08, suggesting that the effect of gender on the panel score is mediated by gender stereotyping.

Table 3: Results of the mediation analysis: review reports

Independ Variable	Dependent variable	Unst. Coef.		St. Coef.		Sig.	95% CI for B	
		B	Std. E.	Beta	t		LB	UB
(1) Gender	Panel score	0.094	0.021	0.080	4.403	0	0.052	0.137
(2) Gender	Negate	-0.090	0.039	-0.042	-2.302	0.021	-0.166	-0.013
Gender	Superlatives	0.116	0.039	0.055	2.992	0.003	0.04	0.193
Gender	Agentic	-0.058	0.039	-0.027	-1.486	0.137	-0.134	0.018
Gender	Communal	-0.072	0.039	-0.034	-1.845	0.065	-0.148	0.005
(3) Gender	Panel score	0.039	0.015	0.033	2.604	0.009	0.01	0.069
Negate		-0.307	0.008	-0.551	-39.347	0	-0.323	-0.292
Superlatives		0.130	0.008	0.233	17.241	0	0.115	0.145
Agentic		-0.129	0.008	-0.231	-16.553	0	-0.144	-0.113
Communal		0.035	0.007	0.062	4.703	0	0.02	0.049

(iii) *Language use in the application texts*

In the last step we look at the language used in the proposal, which as we showed elsewhere also influences the panel scores (Van den Besselaar & Mom 2022). In contrast to other studies (Kolev et al. 2020) we there did not find an effect of gender, but here we use a more elaborated model, in which language use is included as a mediating variable (fig 2).

Figure 2: Panel score by gender and language use in application text as mediator

The results of the analysis are in Table 4. We find that gender has an effect on the panel scores, and women score on average lower than men as Table 4, block (1) shows. Women and men also score differently on several of the linguistic categories used (Van den Besselaar & Mom 2022; Markowitz 2019), although not all are statistically significant (block 2). In the multiple regression (block 3), we see that the beta for gender remains significant, but has become considerably lower (0.048 versus 0.080), suggesting that gender specific language use is responsible for a part of the gender differences in the panel scores.

Table 4: Results of the mediation analysis: application text

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Unstandard. Coeff.		St. Coef.		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(1) Gender	Panel Score	0.094	0.021	0.080	4.403	0
(2) Gender	Word count	15.093	34.453	0.008	0.438	0.661
Gender	Words / sentence	0.116	0.039	0.055	2.992	0.003
Gender	Analytic language	-0.003	0.064	-0.001	-0.046	0.963
Gender	Common terms	-1.030	0.241	-0.078	-4.272	0
Gender	Tentative terms	0.107	0.025	0.078	4.273	0
Gender	Certainty terms	0.080	0.013	0.111	6.125	0
Gender	Causal terms	0.049	0.033	0.028	1.516	0.130
(3) Gender		0.057	0.022	0.048	2.633	0.008
Words / sentence		-0.009	0.002	-0.088	-4.264	0
Common terms	Panel score	-0.010	0.002	-0.107	-4.858	0
Tentative terms		0.039	0.017	0.045	2.249	0.025
Certainty terms		0.164	0.031	0.099	5.237	0
Causal terms		0.034	0.012	0.050	2.786	0.005

Conclusions and discussion

The analysis presented in this paper suggest that text analysis is a promising and relevant line of research for science studies.

With the indicators for gender stereotyping deployed in this paper, we were able to identify different levels of gender stereotyping in panels which do moderately strong correlate with the levels of gender bias in the outcomes of the decision-making process. In the mediation analysis we found that language use in the review reports - and consequently gender stereotyping – explains a large part of the effect of gender on the panel scores. Language use indicates the (implicit) opinions of panel members and reviewers about what the position of women in science should be, and this translates into the gender differences in the scores male and female applicants receive and in the final outcome of the selection process. If this is correct, the process of selecting panel members may need to become much more sensitive to levels of gender stereotyping.

Additionally, we addressed gender differences self-presentation: are there differences between men and women in language use in the grant proposals. This seems somewhat the case, and also here we found that part of the gender differences in the panel scores may be due to these differences in language use. One should be aware that we here only looked at some language differences between men and women, and that other aspects of gendered language use need to be included to derive a reliable picture.

Further research will test possible improvements of the stereotyping variables, and also include other linguistic characteristics of the texts. Due to size restrictions, we cannot discuss this more in detail in this short paper.

Another extension of the paper would be the use of more extended models, which may combine the text analysis of grant applications and of review reports with other aspects of the evaluation process, such as the composition of the decision-making panels and committees, and the specific procedures in which the (evaluative) texts play a role.

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